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Work-based integrated learning in the VET programme: Threats to students' readiness

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Abstract

The introduction of Technical and Vocational Education and Training Colleges started with a new qualification called National Certificate (Vocational), NC (V) in 2007 in South Africa. The qualification enables students to be trained in both theory and practice, yet there is an unpreparedness of students at Work-based environment that add to the ever-increasing unemployment rate in the country. The study investigated the threats of unpreparedness for Work-based Learning of students despite qualifying under the NC (V) programme. Curriculum documents were used to track down NC (V) students into the workplace. Face-to-face interviews with lecturers were conducted. The study found that TVET college lecturers are not well prepared to teach both theory and Vocational subjects, which in turn affect the type of throughputs. One major recommendation is to retrain the TVET College lecturers for them to better prepare their students for a world of work.

Keywords

vocational education; national certificate vocational; technical and vocational education and training college; work-based learning

1 Introduction and background

The legislative landscape of the Further Education and Training (FET) College sector has undergone significant changes in South Africa. Public FET Colleges have been renamed Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Colleges, while private FET Colleges have been renamed private Colleges in terms of the *Further Education and Training Colleges Amendment Act, 2013 (Act No. 1 of 2013)*, in Government Gazette No. 36271. As higher education has expanded, there has been increased emphasis on the skills students learn during their time in Higher Education (HE), beyond the knowledge, technical and academic skills related to their subject or indicated by their achieved class of degree (Mason, Williams and Cranmer 2006). As a result, concern to assess and measure the impact of the wider generic skills that students derive from participation in tertiary education has grown. The concept of 'employability' has been most usefully defined recently as 'the ability of an individual to secure and sustain employment and progress within the workplace', recognizing that different types of employment have different 'employability' requirements (Belt *et al.* 2010: 1-5, UK Commission for Employment and Skills, UKCES, 2010: 2-3). However, there is considerable debate about what 'employability skills' are, particularly with reference to 'graduate employability skills'. Research on employers' perceptions of the graduate labour supply has consistently found that although graduate recruiters generally have had a positive impression of graduates overall, they also reported a lack of some capacities in job applicants and recruits, particularly a lack of business awareness and capacity for self-management, as well as skills shortages in STEM subject areas (CBI 2008, CBI and UUK 2009:49).

According to the Strategy for TVET (2016-2021), TVET can equip youth with the skills required to access the world of work, including skills for self-employment. TVET can also improve responsiveness to changing skill-demands by companies and communities, increase productivity and increase wage levels (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, UNESCO, 2016). Education is generally good insurance against unemployment and for an individual to stay in employment.

The TVET Colleges were boosted with funds and had their workshops and laboratories refurbished in order for students to be taught both theory and practical as required by the current industrial norms. This endeavor in itself is aimed at enhancing Work-based learning (WBL) that will eventually pave way for students to fit in industries. The newly introduced course at TVET Colleges is called National Certificate (Vocational), NC (V). The NC (V) started to run in 2007 at a level called National Qualification Framework (NQF) Level 2 and it is a year course that ends at NQF Level 4.

2 Research question

The study was guided by the following research question:

- What are the challenges that TVET College lecturers have in teaching their students?

3 Problem statement

A majority of former Technical College students who are now lecturers mainly occupies TVET Colleges in South Africa. This means that most of the lecturers at TVET College sector are partially qualified. This then makes entry for students into WBL difficult. This paper then presents threats to students' readiness into the world of work having gone under the NC (V) programme.

4 Methodology

The study made use qualitative research method to collect data. Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) documents were used to solicit information (DHET, 2016) of how the NQF Level 4 students are absorbed in TVET Colleges versus those that make the cut to artisanship at industries. The qualitative research was used because it provides an in-depth, rich data and it analyzes peoples' individual and collective social actions, interpretations, beliefs, thoughts and perceptions (Kruger, Du Plessis & Maseko, 2002).

Six TVET College lecturers from six different TVET Colleges in Gauteng province were purposively and randomly selected to take part in the study. Face-to-face interviews were conducted with the lecturers. Three of the TVET College lecturers are only qualified tradesmen whereas the other three lecturers only possess a teacher's qualification. There was only one female (FT1) with experience in Fitting and Turning, two Automotive Repair and maintenance lecturers (AR1 and AR2), one qualified tradesman and the other one being a qualified teacher from University. The same was with the two Electrical Engineering lecturers (EE1 and EE2) lecturers. An Engineering Graphics and Design (EGD) lecturer (EG1) holds a teacher's qualification from a former College of Education. The abbreviations that are shown refer to the codes that were given to lecturers.

5 Findings

5.1 National Vocational Certificate students' intake

Below is the graph that shows the number of students in South Africa who enter artisanship after completing the NC (V) programme from 2013-2016.

Source: (DHET, 2013- 2016)

Figure 1 Students entering artisanship from NC (V) Level 4

The graph above shows an increasing number of students at NC (V) level programme that enters the TVET College sector. In 2013 the number stood at 24 191 and 2014 saw an increase where the number stood at 26 761. Thirty one thousand and nine hundred (31 900) students registered for NC (V) Level 4 in 2015 and in 2016 the number increased to 35 979. This in itself shows the interest of the community in pursuing a career at TVET College sector. The figure below shows the number of students who entered the artisanal programme as of 2013 to 2016.

Source: DHET (2016)

Figure 2 Number of NC (V) Level 4 students entering artisanal programme

The above figure shows the number of students who completed their NC (V) level 4 programme and managed to be absorbed into artisanal programme. The figures are evident

that 54% of the students who did NC (V) Level 4 programmes between 2013 and 2014 managed to enter into the artisan's programme from 2013/2014. This then left 46% of the students wandering outside the programme. On the other hand, 48% of the 2014/2015 intakes managed to make the cut into the artisanal programme, thus leaving 52% having not been successful. In the period of 2015/2016 though, 42% of the enrolled NC (V) Level 4 students made it to the artisanal programme. The figures are very concerning considering the position that government has taken to alleviate poverty and unemployment in the country. To add to that, below is the figure that shows the number of students who completed the artisanal programme.

Source: (DHET, 2016)

Figure 3 Students who have completed artisanal programme

The figure above shows the number of students who entered and completed the artisanal programme as of 2013 and 2016. In the 2013/ 2014 period, 9 560 students could not make it into completing the artisanal programme which is 65% of the intake of that period. In 2014/2015 periods, 51% of the students completed the artisanal programme leaving 49% failing. In the 2015 / 2016 period, more than half of the entire group that entered the artisanal programme completed the programme. Fifty six percent of the 2015/2016 students' intake completed the course leaving behind 44% of the rest failing.

5.2 TVET College lecturers' interview findings

Interviews were conducted in order to try and establish what challenges do lecturers have which could contribute to the low throughput rate of NC (V) Level 4 students who crack it into the work based environment.

It was quite interesting to see that lecturers felt comfortable in the way they are qualified and how they teach. The female lecturer (FT1) who was offering Fitting and turning said: *"I hold a Fitting and turning trade with no teachers qualification and I enjoy working in the workshop"*. She further said: *"I do however, work closely with my colleague who facilitates the theory part who has recently graduated from a university"*. The Automotive and repair maintenance lecturer (AR1) commented: *"I have never been trained on a car engine because I studied at an institution that did not have proper workshop"*. His counterpart from another

institution (AR2) said: “*I possess a diesel trade in Automotive and repair and maintenance but I am reluctant to teach theory as it is boring, and as such my other colleague does the theory part*”. EE1 on the other hand, who holds a Bachelors degree from a Gauteng university and is not a qualified tradesman, said: “*I know that Electrical engineering is broad with sections like transformers and steam engines which I never saw in my career as a student*”. His counterpart EE2, said: “*I am from Eskom and I worked there for a couple of years and as such I love practical, theory to me is boring, it just needs notes that’s all*”. EG1 lecturer said: “*In my 21 years of teaching career, I had to learn a lot by myself because we hardly get developed at this level; therefore I know what is best for my students. I am in the process of implementing AutoCAD because I know that it is the way of the future*”.

6 Discussions and conclusion

The above responses show that lecturers are not trained the same. This then creates a different type of students who qualify with NQF Level 4. With that said, the greatest threat now becomes the quality of qualified students from TVET College who fail to cope and be absorbed in industries. Research on employers’ perceptions of the graduate labour supply has consistently found that although graduate recruiters generally have had a positive impression of graduates overall, they also reported a lack of some capacities in job applicants and recruits, particularly a lack of business awareness and capacity for self-management, as well as skills shortages in STEM subject areas as discussed earlier (CBI 2008, CBI and UUK 2009:49). The findings then call for the retraining of TVET College lecturers to create a culture of learning and teaching to better prepare their students for the world of work.

References

- Belt V., Drake, P. and Chapman, K. (2010) *Employability Skills: A Research and Policy Briefing*, UK Commission for Employment and Skills.
- CBI (2008) *Taking Stock*. CBI Education and Skills Survey 2008. www.cbi.org.uk/pdf/skills_report0408.pdf
- CBI and Universities UK (2009) *Future fit: preparing graduates for the world of work* <http://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/Publications/Documents/FutureFit.PDF>
- Department of Higher Education and Training. (2013-2016). *Statistics on Post-School Education and Training in South Africa*. Government printers. Pretoria
- Kruger, A.G., Du Plessis, S. & Maseko, J.S (2002). *School Management* Pretoria: University of South Africa
- Mason, G., Williams, G. and Cranmer, S. (2006) *Employability Skills Initiatives in Higher Education: What Effects Do They Have On Graduate Labour Market Outcomes?* London: National Institute of Economic and Social Research. http://www.niesr.ac.uk/pdf/061006_91251.pdf
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, UNESCO, (2016). *Strategy for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) (2016-2021)*. Education sector. France

Biographical notes

Dr Samuel Khoza is a lecturer at the University of the Witwatersrand in the Educational Information and engineering Technology. He started his lecturing career way bay at a TVET College in 1999 before moving to Walter Sisulu University in 2009. He currently supervises BEd Honours, masters as well as PhD students in the TVET field as well as Information and Communications Technology education.